

Optimisation of FOP and WT fibroblast cell seeding for ALP assay

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Aims:

C2C12 cells did not produce a large fold change in ALP expression following ligand administration (see [previous post](#)), therefore we will try to use FOP fibroblasts instead as these have a greater signalling response to BMP ligands. In order to complete this assay I must work out how many cells to seed in order to get a confluent well after 7 days of treatment (the expected period of time required for later compound assays).

Experimental details

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Frozen [GM00513](#) (FOP, henceforth FOP-513) and [AG06103](#) (WT, henceforth FIB6103) fibroblasts were thawed by addition of excess FOP medium (EMEM + 1x NEA MEM, 10% FCS), pelleting by centrifugation, and resuspension in FGM.

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Both cell lines were confluent. Cells were split and seeded in technical triplicate into Corning 6103 96 well plates in the following concentrations: 5000, 2500, 1250, 625, 312.5, 156.25 cells / well in 100µL FOP medium.

FOP513 = P14

FIB6103 = P13

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Plate was imaged in Celigo. Although by eye the cells are very thin and hard to see, the Celigo seems to be able to quantify them well (see Figure 1).

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Cells were stained as follows:

- Make 5mL PBS + 1:1000 PI (stock 1.0mg/mL in water), 1:1000 Hoechst 33342, 1:2000 Calcein AM (8mM stock solution)
- Vortex solution for 10s
- Replace growth medium with PBS staining solution
- Image on Celigo after 25 min incubation (in the dark)

Results/Conclusions

An incubation period of only 25 minutes is sufficient for propidium iodide to stain cells, so here only Calcein AM can be considered. In future a longer incubation period for propidium iodide will be required.

Considering which wells are confluent, and in which wells overcrowding has led to a decrease in Calcein AM positive cells: For an 8 day assay a seeding density of 625-1250 FIB6103 cells and 1250-2500 FOP513 cells would be optimal.

Figure 1 – Panel A: Demonstration of the capacity for the Celigo image cytometer to quantify the confluence of cells which are difficult to see with the naked eye. Scale bars are 250 μ m.

Panel B: Confluence of wild-type (*fib6103*) and FOP (*fop513*) fibroblasts seeded at the indicated densities in a 96 well plate, after 3 days of culture. Scale bars are 1mm.

Figure 2 – Wild-type and FOP fibroblasts were seeded in the indicated densities into wells of a 96 well plate. Following 8 days of culture cells were stained with Calcein AM (green), and Hoechst 3342 (blue) and fluorescently imaged. Number of cells was quantified using the Celigo image cytometer analysis software on the basis of Hoechst 33342 staining of nuclei and from this the percentage of Calcein AM (viable) cells was calculated. Scale bars are 1mm.